

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DIDACTIC ISSUES OF SOLVING THE PROBLEM OF PROTECTING THE PURITY OF THE GLOBAL SOCIAL-SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT OF THE TIME

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Abstract

The article argues that the preservation of the purity of the social and moral environment is a global problem of the time. It is shown that, as in physical-biological ecology, there can be a crisis in social-spiritual ecology. Searching for ways to insure against such a threat and perfecting the education system in this direction is of particular importance at a time when banal culture is on the rise and foreign influences on our national-spiritual environment are intensifying.

In research work, it is considered important to focus on two directions in the formation of the process of protecting the purity of the social and moral environment as a subsystem of the educational system, and this is argued on the basis of the generalizations of the research materials. The mentioned first direction is to raise the level of cultural-spiritual perfection, self-awareness and will of people, which is determined by giving priority to a new pedagogical way of thinking in the formation of the educational space. The second direction is to refine the cultural-spiritual environment in which people live, to solve the problems of spiritual ecology in a systematic way, that is, whether the education system or the cultural-spiritual life of young people should create such an environment that the ability of this environment to react against negative influences is strong, and there is a relationship between people and external influences. to form a protective area.

Keywords: socio-spiritual ecology, globalization, social instinct, mentality, nationality, national-philosophical thought, social self-defense, self-awareness, moral adaptation.

Relevance of the research topic

The systemic-structural approach suggests that it is impossible to avoid the influence of the globalized world. In fact, there is no need for it, because this is the logic of civilization. Therefore, we have faced the need to find ways to protect national and moral values, and this process is constantly diversifying. This phenomenon is eternal in nature.

Despite what has been said, the need to be a participant in the globalization process and the fact that the problem caused by it has an eternal nature logically determines the urgency of solving the "problem of protecting the purity of the social and moral environment of the era with a global character". Therefore, "Didactic issues of solving the problem of protecting the purity of the social-spiritual environment of the global nature" is one of the relevant cognitive issues aimed at solving the said problem, and in the study of such an issue, the negative moral-ecological effects of national-spiritual values under the conditions of globalization can be selected as a subject.

Interpretation of the summation of research materials

Although ecological education has recently found its place in scientific pedagogy as one of the subsystems of education, it is possible to find information directly and indirectly related to this concept in examples of oral

folk creativity and works of our classics. "In scientific pedagogy, the main ideas and most important directions of ecological education, which are given as components (subsystems) of education, are systematized with reference to ethnopedagogy. Educating the generation in the spirit of love for our national and moral values, guiding them to the purification of the natural and social environment is one of the most important tasks ahead. Among these tasks, it is important to familiarize our young people with the ethno-pedagogical materials, which are considered as one of our irreplaceable and unique national values, and to arm them with the knowledge here. [10; 526]

It should be noted that although there are many fields and divisions of modern ecology, there is no unanimity of opinion about the concept of ecology. World scientists tried to reveal the essence of this concept and gave different definitions to the mentioned concept. According to our subjective understanding, the general meaning of ecology is the interaction between the environment and living organisms, including humans and society. It can be clearly seen from the interpretation of the concept of personality that the essence of the concept of ecology includes the impact of various organisms on the environment and the preservation of the purity of the social and moral environment.

Modern pedagogy views personality as a complete mental system, where biological and social characteristics are inseparable. Being a product of social life, personality is also a living organism. The relationship between sociological and biological in personality formation and behavior is quite complex and does not have the same effect on personality in different periods of human development.

Personality is considered a set of biogenetic, socio-genetic and psychogenetic elements in modern pedagogy and psychology. Personality is a form of manifestation of a number of qualities and conditions of human existence. Man is a general concept. It is a category of biological species. An individual is a human type of biological entity. Personality is a social entity that distinguishes a person from other biological creatures. The social structure and culture in which a person is brought up and participates determine the social nature of the personality.

In modern pedagogy and psychology, they did not have an unambiguous approach to the concept of personality. The majority of researchers believe that a person with unique individual characteristics, a certain way of thinking, behavior, feelings, social attitudes and communication, formed during his life, is called a personality (there are other definitions and ideas about personality). According to L. I. Bojovich, one of the important criteria that gives the opportunity to characterize the personality is precisely the understanding of behavioral motives, their conscious conditioning by social norms. Understanding motives has psychological roots. In this period, self-consciousness as a special instance of personality is formed and "I-concept" is formed. Self-consciousness is multifaceted, but two aspects - psychological self-portrait (I-image) and self-relation occupy a special place in its structure. They distinguish three main functions of self-consciousness - self-awareness, self-improvement and the search for the meaning of life. In the process of forming a person as a personality, self-consciousness develops in interaction with moral consciousness. Self-consciousness and moral consciousness - the "I-concept" of the personality is essentially based on these dimensions. His relations with other people, work, things and himself begin to be systematically formed. [3;318-319]

It should be emphasized here that the national philosophical idea expresses the relationship between the national "I" and the world, in contrast to reflecting the world's relationship with a person, a person's personal, individual relationship with the world. Just as the national "I" is different from the individual "I" and the universal "I", so is its relation to the world. The individual "I" is richer because it is able to contain universal and national "I". However, the individual "I" cannot always understand itself. The way of self-awareness of individual individuals contains only certain elements of national and universal self-awareness. Rather, in individual self-awareness, the world component, the intuitive component, the irrational component covers a larger area. Universal consciousness, universal self-awareness is a rationalized expression of people's attitude to the world for centuries. Human knowledge about the world is manifested in different hierarchical levels. [4; 383]

Just as a person is not just a physical-biological being, the environment that surrounds him is not just a natural environment. As a social being, a person interacts with other people and society in general, and these relationships have a significant impact on his formation. In this sense, human ecology includes biological ecology as well as social and spiritual ecology. Although a person's spirituality has genetic foundations, it is mainly formed by the influence of the social-spiritual environment, and here the cultural-spiritual life of the society and the cultural aspects of the environment in which a person grows up play a prominent role. [3; 88] As a bio-sociological being, he studies humanity in society and confirms his humanity in society through his behavior, morality, and interaction with others. Behavior in society is one of the moral duties of a person. Fulfillment of this task also helps in establishing human relations. People who perform their moral duties normally and are able to establish normal human relations are called people with good morals. The path of a person's rise to the level of universality follows the following scheme: Man⇒Society⇒Humanity. [7;127]

Spirituality is an individual category that reflects a person's inner world, character, attitude to people, the surrounding world, and events. Spirituality is the intellectual and natural essence of a person, which characterizes his spiritual upbringing, inner world and expresses himself. This includes, first of all, human honor, dignity, conscience, national identity, civic zeal, selflessness, respect for national and moral values, our past, history, language, culture, customs and deep study of our traditions, as well as spiritual qualities such as kindness, compassion and caring, sensitivity and humanism, tolerance, modernity, respect and love for people, and love for the motherland. Morality is "the way a person looks, the way he looks." Spirituality is an indicator of the richness of a person's inner world. The health of a spiritually rich person is also perfect. A spiritually rich person enjoys life and lives comfortably. A spiritually rich person is able to endure all kinds of difficulties and make the right decisions even in the most difficult moments. [6; 310-311]

The more important it is to develop a person's mind and thinking, the more important and necessary it is to form the spiritual world, spirituality, and positive moral qualities of a person. Arming the young generation with a system of knowledge and creating a worldview in it is not enough in itself, educating morally perfect and morally pure citizens means strengthening the foundation and foundations of our society. Moral development occurs as the final result of moral education and indicates the level of moral education of the young generation. [2; 411]

Among the elements of education that ensure the normal behavior of a person within society and are part of the complex education system, the following have a special place: education of justice; education of truthfulness; confidence education; training to do the right thing; education of intelligence and intelligence; education to correctly understand the rules; health education; education in the spirit of struggle; thrift education; education of generosity; education of the culture of service to the people with dignity; humanistic education;

reliable human education; education of communication culture; education of will; education of the unity of material and spiritual; environmental education; Azerbaijan education. [5;350-362] The listed elements are synthesized as parts of the unit and directed to the implementation of the "enabling function" in the protection of national moral values, resisting negative moral-ecological effects.

Pedagogical literature mentions three groups of tasks of moral education: 1) formation of moral consciousness, moral imagination, understanding and judgments in the young generation; 2) formation of moral feelings and attitudes; 3) formation of moral behavior. Moral education is divided into many branches, components, constituent parts, which have their own specific tasks. Thus, patriotism education - love for the motherland, native land, family, patriotism; internationalism education - solidarity with different peoples, respect for their feelings; education of simplicity and humility - to behave simply in the younger generation, not to brag about one's success, not to look down on others; companionship and friendship education - to strengthen the bonds of friendship and friendship among students, to help each other, to share in each other's joys and sorrows, loyalty in friendship; education of honesty and truthfulness - being sincere in relations with peers, teachers, parents, telling the truth, not telling lies, etc. creates conditions for the development of qualities. [2; 413]

In the conditions of globalization, it would be beneficial for the common cause to put forward an idea about the ways of determining the options for protection from the negative moral-ecological effects that national moral values can carry. One of the most urgent problems in modern times is finding the optimal ratio between national self-isolation and globalization. Along with science, technology, technology, and universal values, the process of globalization tends to affect the cultural and moral factors that determine the national identity. [4; 406]

As in the physical-biological ecology, a crisis can occur in the social-spiritual ecology. Therefore, the preservation of the purity of the social and moral environment is one of the global problems of the time. At a time when banal culture is on the rise, foreign influences on our national-spiritual environment are intensifying, we must be familiar with the problems of social-spiritual ecology, and in order to protect ourselves from foreign influences entering our social life from outside, we must form national self-awareness qualities, social self-defense instinct in our youth, and the spirituality within a person around him must be a protective environment for. [6; 25-27] For this purpose, we need to know what we need to protect, define appropriate criteria and draw attention to those criteria in the educational process.

Our great leader Heydar Aliyev said the following about the moral education of young people, about spirituality in his speech at the First All-Republic Forum of Azerbaijan Youth: "There has been high spirituality in all the stages of the history of our people, in the past centuries. It is their high spirituality and high deeds that make the figures from our past history famous in the

world today and serve as examples for us... One of the main tasks facing our young people is the issue of moral education... it is necessary to carry out moral education constantly and educate our young people in the spirit of high spirituality. Universal values, national and moral values of the Azerbaijani people should be understood by every young person. Nothing can happen where there is no spirituality... Our youth must be educated in the national spirit, they must be educated on the basis of our national and moral values. Our youth should know our history well, know the past well, know our language well, and know our national values well. A young person who does not know our national values and traditions well cannot be a patriot." This is the content of spiritual education! Now the important practical task is to purify the cultural and spiritual environment in which people live, to systematically solve the problem of spiritual ecology. [1]

Scientific sources emphasize the presence of two important points in Heydar Aliyev's approach to issues of spirituality:

1. Conscience, sincerity, caring for others, putting public and national interests above personal interests and greed, not being indifferent to the fate and pain of others, compassion, etc. assessment of moral values and principles;

2. Appreciation of our spiritual sources, spiritual culture, moral principles and values.

Here we are talking about the historical, cultural, spiritual and moral values of the Azerbaijani people, oral folk literature, literature and art, philosophical and social opinion, centuries-old artistic culture of the Azerbaijani people, and the historical memory of the nation as a whole. All these and other unnamed values contain extremely important information about the spiritual life and moral principles of our great ancestors, the moral and spiritual roots of the nation. [1]

Studying the ideas, thoughts and sayings of the Great Citizen of Azerbaijan leads us to the conclusion that all elements of the moral life of the nation, the moral and spiritual world of the personality are present in his ideological heritage. Based on this rich heritage, a fundamental theoretical model of the spiritual world of the growing generation and a unique code of moral principles of society can be developed.

We cannot accept any quality in our past as a national invariant, positive aspect. It cannot be denied that real national qualities are qualities that keep the nation alive and develop it. At this time, we cannot forget that we should serve our present and our future, our national-spiritual ideal more than the past, and be based on the ideology filtered through the prism of national consciousness. [4; 408]

Such an ideology exists in Azerbaijan as well: Azerbaijanism has become the national-political ideology of the Azerbaijani state. Our state has a strategic plan in the mentioned direction, a plan that envisages the creation of a protective zone between our citizens and foreign influence. As we emphasized above, it is necessary to take the concept of "Azerbaijanism" as one of the components of education and clearly show its place in the complex education system. For this purpose, the essence, scientific principles, methodological,

psychological and philosophical foundations of Azerbaijani education, ways of instilling them in schoolchildren should be thoroughly investigated. The development of the concept of Azerbaijanism, the correct and consistent implementation of this policy not only puts an end to negativity that may occur on ethnic grounds, but also promotes the formation of a new healthy society. It should not be forgotten that "the factors that unite people are always more and stronger than the factors that separate them, so the factors that unite nations are more and stronger than the factors that separate them." [6; 163] It should not be objected that in order to clean the society normally, it is necessary to rely on this main fact.

In scientific sources, useful recommendations about the work to be done for the implementation of the policy of Azerbaijanism have taken place. [2-6] It is believed that the implementation of the mentioned policy will be possible by doing the following works: accurately study and analyze the number of each ethnic group, its position in society, places of settlement, social composition, demographic situation; to choose facts and events, all factors that are in the interests of all ethnic groups; to choose facts and events, factors that create conditions and excuses for separatism, that correspond to the interests of only some groups, and that cannot be accepted by all; distinguish between bilateral and multilateral issues and factors that can be agreed upon; to investigate and test the possibility of bringing certain disagreements to a level; to bring to the fore unifying facts and events, factors that are considered decisive in the life of society, to carry out effective work in the direction of gradual reduction and elimination of divisive facts and events, factors; to do every job fairly, not to allow ethnic discrimination, while implementing measures necessary for economic-social, cultural-educational, scientific-educational and human life; to create conditions for the representation of worthy representatives of all ethnic groups in the state management process. [6;163-164].

Academician S. Khalilov writes that Azerbaijanism is one of the main components of our national ideology today. Azerbaijanism should be the main guiding ideology in the way of life, morals, spirituality, language, religion, literature - in all areas of spiritual culture. Oral folk literature, handicrafts, national music, all manifestations of the nation's cultural and spiritual existence should be closely united around a single idea today. [4; 410]

It can be said with certainty that the state of Azerbaijan assumed the function of preserving the national entity from the day it regained its independence. Heydar Aliyev used to say: "... The education of the growing generation, the formation of a morally rich, idealistic, high moral personality is a very important task facing our society today. This is a complex problem, and in its solution ... the school plays a very big role. The foundation of a person's outlook is laid at school. His character is formed, the foundations of ideas, spiritual and moral foundations are created. Under the influence of the school... qualities such as a person's conviction, love for work, high spirituality and humanism, patriotism and internationalism are brought up... Preparing the

growing generation for work and creative activity for the welfare of society is one of the main directions of the school's educational work. Now the important practical task is to purify the cultural and spiritual environment in which people live, to systematically solve the problem of spiritual ecology. [6; 320-321]

In accordance with the strategic plan of the state, the focus should be on optimizing the educational programs applied in the education system in order to increase the level of cultural and moral perfection, self-awareness and will of people, to strengthen the ability to react to external influences, and to form their social instinct. [4; 410]

The function of the school and the attitude towards it must change. If we want to preserve the school not only as a means of education, but also as a center of education, we must first think about preserving the national-cultural-spiritual environment. Education itself should become a part of the national ideology as a whole.

Heydar Aliyev focused on the components and functions of moral education and showed the ways of its implementation. According to him, the highly developed sense of responsibility of the personality is one of the important conditions of not violating the norms of law and morality and not acting improperly against the moral foundations of the nation. Therefore, education of the sense of responsibility in schoolchildren should be an integral part of moral education. In our opinion, this issue should be at the center of activity of all structures involved in education of schoolchildren. According to H. Aliyev, relying on the moral potential of the nation and society, uniting all layers of the people and society of Azerbaijan is one of the important functions of moral education. The initial stage of the implementation of this unity is the formation of a high sense of responsibility in individuals for the present and future of the motherland, the country, and the nation's tomorrow. The second step can be organized by the moral and moral unity of the nation and society. If the moral and moral unity of the people is ensured, then the solution of many social and political issues becomes easier and can be realized.

By the way, let's note that both due to the high level of development of science and technology, as well as due to the degree of settlement and social orientation of the market economy for several centuries, the Western world, without a doubt, occupies a leading position. However, modernity cannot be determined only by technology and economic indicators. "Thousands of years of spiritual evolution of mankind played a greater role in the formation of modern man, perhaps, than scientific and technical progress." [9] Some people look for the reasons why the countries representing the Eastern world lag behind the leading Western countries in the economic race based on modern technology in the traditional way of thinking. The point is that in modern times, the absolutization of individuality in the way of thinking and giving preference to one side or the other cannot lead to any positive results. Modern thinking even involves "reconciling" radically different ways of thinking of different civilizations, combining their progressive aspects. [4]

Based on the summary of materials obtained from scientific sources, we can say that the ways of eliminating the negative impact of scientific and technical progress on morality and spirituality can be grouped into three main directions: 1) to consider in advance the possible negative consequences during the planning of the application of science and new technologies to production and life; 2) compensating the necessary negative effects of computerization and mechanization with other means (religion, morality, art, etc.); 3) to prepare new, intensive methods and forms of spiritual education corresponding to the requirements of scientific and technical progress and to use the opportunities opened by scientific and technical progress in order to increase its mass. It has been proven in social experience that when moral prohibitions and rational thinking and action, inertia force and driving force come together, comprehensive development and moral deformation of a person are not allowed. Of course, people always strive for innovation. But there should be a sense of internal resistance to every innovation. When this feeling is excessive, stagnation occurs, when it is weak, arbitrariness and anarchy arise. In fact, it is clear that such a task is ahead: on the one hand, a return to national roots, national and moral values, and on the other hand, to adapt to the modern requirements set by scientific and technical development and information society. It is also clear that the processes taking place in the individual-spiritual world of each person remind us of the problems related to the spiritual life of the nation as a whole. As Carl Jung wrote, "the psychology of the individual corresponds to the psychology of the nation as a whole. [12; 28]

The relationship between ideology and education should be highlighted. Education is aimed at individuals and tries to acquire existing cultural and moral values for each individual. Ideology, on the other hand, is at the level of the nation and theoretically forms this system of values for the sake of social development as a whole. Therefore, as in every civilized country, the educational process in Azerbaijan is carried out on the basis of national ideology. From this point of view, the pedagogical process and the pedagogical theory are not

completely independent, they must be reconstructed at each stage of development in accordance with the requirements of the national-philosophical thought and ideology. Today, there is a need to develop such a reconstruction from both theoretical and practical-technological aspects. [3; 417]

Work in the field of moral education in the school should be carried out in the following directions:

1. Forming moral consciousness in schoolchildren (being able to distinguish between good and evil, benevolence and malice, beauty and ugliness, real and fake, national-spiritual awareness, national identity, homeland, national bigotry, self-sacrifice, loyalty to one's roots, etc.)

2. Creating moral feelings in schoolchildren (conscience, honor, merit, honor, debt, trust, responsibility, patriotism, citizenship, etc.)

3. Forming a moral position in schoolchildren (showing self-sacrifice in difficult moments of life, having a good relationship, treating people with respect, care and sensitivity, helping and helping, etc.)

4. Forming a moral character in schoolchildren (patience and restraint, tolerance, organization, precision, loyalty, courage, courage, culture and politeness, simplicity and humility, honesty and truthfulness, friendship and companionship, mercy and kindness etc.)

5. Forming moral behavior, customs and habits in schoolchildren (being ready to serve the country, the people, respect the customs and traditions of the people, demonstrate moral behavior, make correct and independent decisions, have polite and polite communication and behavior, be kind to people) is manifested in his behavior and actions. This manifests itself in behavior and action, that moral qualities are not simply memorized, these qualities are formed in action and behavior.

Age, individual, psychological and sexual characteristics should be taken into account in the spiritual upbringing of students. [5;313]

Based on research generalizations, it is possible to formulate such a schematic description:

System-structural approach, anthropological pedagogical views are based on the philosophical-pedagogical idea aimed at theoretically determining the ways of protecting national-spiritual values from foreign influences in the schematic description of research generalization.

In the conditions of globalization, the development of new technologies aimed at the formation of national and moral values and the development of emotional and voluntary abilities of schoolchildren constitute the operational aspect of education. The main didactic unit of this process is the methods of training.

It should also be noted that the natural, social and cultural abilities of a person are organically connected with the potential of his internal activity. This activity acquires a certain orientation and corresponding characteristics according to the level of moral and spiritual values of the personality.

In the globalized world, moral values and paradigms of social cognition are changing. The content and theory of self-education, self-organization and self-awareness (synergetics) are gaining more and more positions. Such changes are based on ideas. These may include:

- the systematicity and integrity of the world and scientific knowledge about it;
- non-linearity, multivariate, irreversibility of development;
- self-organization, self-education and self-awareness of living systems;
- the interaction of chaos and order, necessity and chance;
- improvement and development of the social system (society), spiritual values in the process of dialogue between man and nature. [6;197-198]

Technologicalization of moral and spiritual values using national traditions should be based on its main characteristics (functionality, logical content, instrumental-technological). In order to improve the students' abilities related to moral and spiritual values, the components containing motivation, intellectual and procedural skills should be selected and special conditions should be created for their development.

In scientific sources [5; 205-206] it is shown that more effective results are obtained when the consideration of national traditions in the formation of moral and spiritual values is carried out in successive stages such as diagnostic, familiarization, motivating, practical-creative.[8]

Scientific-theoretical novelty of the research

1. Spirituality, as a personal integral characteristic of a person, implies the existence of the volume of his quality indicators and his personal characteristics, manifests itself as an indicator of internal psychological stability against events that try to destroy his personal qualities and characteristics;

2. Spirituality cannot be "externally" shaped as a derivative of inner inclinations and personal strength. They begin to form from the inside, develop and spread,

find a certain orientation to get out of their limits, and create an incentive for self-education, spiritual improvement, and moral development in a person;

3. In the formation of the process of protecting the purity of the socio-spiritual environment as a subsystem of the education system, it is important to focus on two directions: to raise the level of people's cultural-spiritual perfection, self-awareness and will, and to purify the cultural-spiritual environment in which people live.

The result

The following results were obtained during the research:

1. Preservation of the purity of the socio-spiritual environment is a global problem of the time, and didactic issues have a special place in its solution;

2. Searching for ways to insure against the threat of an unwanted crisis situation, and making the education system perfect in this direction, is urgent at a time when the vulgar culture is walking around and foreign influences on our national-spiritual environment are intensifying, that is, the "social-spiritual ecological education process" as a subsystem, it should take its place in the real pedagogical process;

3. Raising the level of cultural and moral perfection, self-awareness and will of people in the process of implementation of education should be focused as an important link;

4. In order to form a protective field between people and external influences, the problems of moral ecology should be systematically solved.

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